

Epistemic Insight

THE EPISTEMIC INSIGHT DIGEST

SPECIAL EDITION
SPRING 2023

FACULTY OF
ARTS, HUMANITIES
& EDUCATION

CONTENTS

Editor's Note

4

Search Engines and Their Need to Evolve

6

Ethan A Georgiou

Psychology and Interdisciplinarity: Potential for Epistemic Insights

10

Nick Zuppa

Practical's Place in Pedagogy: Igniting a Passion for Science

16

Angus Hope

Co-creation During a Lasar Work Placement

22

Buffy-Lucy Jennings

EI Students in Research: Research Placements at the LASAR Centre

28

Aryn Litchfield

EDITOR'S NOTE

This Special edition of the digest brings together a collection of articles written by students and recent graduates, sharing their insights and experiences while exploring Epistemic Insight. We are grateful for the continued effort of those involved in the epistemic insight initiative and its wider community for helping to communicate the themes, pedagogies, and concepts contained in this edition. Our collective 'future of knowledge' might be an uncertain one, however, reflecting on these articles and the wider discussions they evoke, indicates that our efforts are helping to facilitate and create the fertile ground for that future to bear fruit - The fruit of being epistemically insightful.

Special thanks to the following contributors for making this edition of the digest possible:

- Prof Berry Billingsley
- Aryn Litchfield
- Nick Zuppa
- Ethan. A Georgiou
- Angus Hope
- Buffy-Lucy Jennings

And a special thanks to - you the reader - for joining us on this journey.

Happy reading,

Aryn Litchfield

LASAR Research fellow and Coordinator.

Epistemic Insight

What about if uni students from different disciplines could form a group and tackle these challenges together. Why don't we do more of that?

FIND OUT MORE AT
[futureofknowledge.com](http://futureofknowledge.com/knowledge-labs)
[/knowledge-labs](http://knowledge-labs)

 Canterbury
Christ Church
University

SEARCH ENGINES AND THEIR NEED TO EVOLVE

Ethan A Georgiou

Abstract

The evolution of Search Engines has been nothing short of stagnant regarding how it presents its content to the user and to how epistemically beneficial the content it provides is to the user. This article will touch upon how AI can be utilized to overcome this deficiency in learning potential left in the wake of this evolutionary plateau.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence is oft considered the inexorable way of the future, a necessary steppingstone to further humanity on its path of progression and evolution. However, with every advancement there are always questions that arise as to whether the path that we forge is the truly to the benefit to civilization, or merely a fruitless venture that is akin to self-indulgence more so than enlightenment. If we, as a species, are to continue this dedication to embedding the concept into our culture then we should perhaps first ask questions as to what will this mean for humanity?

We are already seeing advancements and implementations in machine learning in certain fields. Using algorithms to predict market fluctuations across the stock exchange. Using algorithms to generate art inspired by samples found in the far corners of the internet. Using algorithms to determine what actions healthcare workers should take to ensure the wellbeing of their ever-growing lists of patients. Be it for personal profit, efficiency of procedure or guarantees of safety, these implementations follow the idea that AI is naught but a tool. However, one question that most have yet to ask is: how can we use AI to better ourselves? The industry is fixated on the principle that AI systems are merely means for a purpose; a system to solve a problem better than any human could.

Epistemic Insight and I

Epistemic Insight rather, wishes to let AI help us get better at solving problems for ourselves. Epistemic Insight is an organization whose name semantically translates to 'knowledge about knowledge' and consists of people who look to improve the way we learn about the world around us. One of the ways it proposes to better education is with the implementation of AI in search engines. The principle of incorporating AI into a search engine, a 'Smarter Search Engine' if you will, is to provide a resource that enriches our capacity for learning. I first encountered and became involved in the project was at EI's The Future of Knowledge exhibition at London's Royal Society of Chemistry which I helped to host. Before the event took place I conversed with Lee, one of the developers, who explained to me what he was working on and showed me the progress that has so far been made thus far on their prototype and as a fellow computer scientist we also discussed how the algorithm functioned specifically to achieve its intended goals.

The Ever-Important Search Engine

A search engine at its core is nothing more than an algorithm that as its namesake suggests, searches (Yang, *n.d.*). One provides a query then an algorithm parses the string of characters of said query, essentially breaking down the query into individual constituents such as turning a sentence into a sequence of noun and verb phrases. It then searches its vast domains across the world to find the most alike results and finishes by feeding them back to the user in order of likeness and frequency of access.

For what is, in principle, a simple resource the search engine has become something people instinctively gravitate towards for learning and discovery (*Kurniasih et al, 2018*), with many taking its existence utterly for granted; the mere thought of not using a service such as Google as alien and archaic. Yet despite its usefulness and our everyday dependency on search engines the service has a key limitation, one that has been present since its initial inception decades ago: it will only search for what you ask for. Now at first this notion sounds like nothing but beneficial, who wants to have the results for their query filled with the irrelevant? However, regarding education, this principle can surprisingly hinder and diminish one's ability to learn.

Why is the Sky Blue?

Let's take for example the question "why is the sky blue?", a question that I'm sure that most if not all have asked once in their life. If you were to ask this query to a search engine such as Google the first results you would be from NASA and the MET office, or perhaps a link to a YouTube video explanation. These results all tell you effectively that same thing: that the sky is blue due to shorter wavelengths of light that we perceive as blue being scattered more by molecules in the air than other wavelengths of light. This is what we have come to expect and initially seems like a perfectly adequate service for learning. But here is where its limitations are exposed for everyone to see.

We have all these results saying the same thing to the user, all answering the question from the discipline and perspective of physics and science because that is what the query matched to in terms of likeness. The user would walk away from this interaction now knowing the answer to their question but what if they could walk away with even greater insight. What if the search engine instead of providing these redundancies, presented the user with opportunities to interact with content from multiple perspectives? Thereby affording them the opportunity to develop a greater degree of insight and encourage the type of 'research agency' that is especially necessary to help users critically assess knowledge that is complex in nature.

The Impenetrable Mind

There is a concept called 'qualia' which can be defined as a purely subjective, conscious experience (*Tye, 2021*). The emotions we feel are examples of qualia. Pain and pleasure are forms of qualia. Another example is colour, like the fact that we see the sky to be the colour blue. Qualia only exists in one's mind, it cannot be transferred to another person; how do you describe the colour blue to someone who is blind? How do you know if your subjective experience of the sky being blue is the same as someone else's? What if what they perceive to be blue is what you perceive to be red and how would you even communicate this discrepancy?

Steps for an Insightful Future

We have now looked at the question of "why is the sky blue?" from a philosophical, psychological and linguistical perspective. All these perspectives are valid in answering this question so why doesn't the search engine provide them? This is the key problem that the 'Smarter Search Engine' is hoping to solve by not just returning results based on syntax likeness and how often a linked is clicked, but also all the different angles a question can be approached allowing for a more insightful approach to learning. This concept of promoting multi-disciplinary answering to questions and the benefits it will bring us has already been touched upon from members of EI (*Billingsley and Fraser, 2018*).

Reflecting on a common tautology: "we don't know what we don't know." People won't always know all the different ways a question can be answered and to what paths of erudition they will lead to, but perhaps AI can help us on our journey to them.

References

- Yang, T (n.d.) *'Web Search Engines: Practice and Experience'*. University of California at Santa Barbara. Apostolos Gerasoulis, Rutgers University. [Online] Available at: sites.cs.ucsb.edu/~tyang/papers/bookchaptersearch.pdf
- Kurniasih, N et al (2018) *'The utilization of search engines by students of the Library and Information Science Program at Universitas Padjadjaran'*. In: J. Phys.: Conf Ser. 1114 012085. [Online] Available at: iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1114/1/012085/pdf
- Tye, M (2021) 'Qualia'. In: *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Edward N. Zalta (ed.) [Online] Available at: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2021/entries/qualia> (Accessed 24 October, 2022)
- Billingsley, B and Fraser, S (2018) *'Towards an Understanding of Epistemic Insight: the Nature of Science in Real World Contexts and a Multidisciplinary Arena'*. [Editorial]. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-018-9776-x>

Epistemic Insight

How do we solve the **Big Questions, opportunities** and **problems** of today and tomorrow?

What about if uni students from different disciplines could form a group and tackle these challenges together. Why don't we do more of that?

FIND OUT MORE AT
[futureofknowledge.com](http://futureofknowledge.com/knowledge-labs)
[/knowledge-labs](https://www.instagram.com/knowledge-labs)

 Canterbury
Christ Church
University

PSYCHOLOGY AND INTERDISCIPLINARITY: POTENTIAL FOR EPISTEMIC INSIGHTS

Nick Zuppa

Abstract

Psychology stands in a rather peculiar position within the academic disciplines, unifying a diverse number of ontological schools of knowledge under one banner. This article makes the case that other disciplines would profit from an increased interdisciplinary exchange with psychology. This article wanted to demonstrate that psychology has the potential to further our understanding of natural-scientific inquiry through the re-introduction of subjective experience into the various natural-science disciplines, for example concerning future interactions with artificial agents. Similarly, psychology has the potential to help inform the humanities about the biological substrate subjective experience is built upon, as in the example outlined regarding potential neuropsychological mechanisms driving social phenomena such as political polarization. Psychology can therefore help those two schools of thought within academia to communicate with each other.

How psychology can help develop epistemic insight through interdisciplinary exchanges

Psychology stands in a rather peculiar position within the academic disciplines, unifying a diverse number of ontological schools of knowledge under one banner (Wieczorek, 2021). With sub-disciplines within psychology being as diverse as psychoanalysis, cognitive psychology, social psychology, evolutionary psychology, cognitive neuropsychology and neuroscience among others, there is a variety of first principles existing within the field. Examining epistemic insight through the lens of psychology identifies it as being very diverse, spanning various methods of investigation such as phenomenological-, critical-, social-constructivist-, functionalist- and biological-approaches (Barsalou, 2014; Durrheim, 1997; Kalat, 2015; Spiegelberg & Murray, 1973). Epistemic insight can be broadly defined as knowledge about knowledge and in particular, knowledge about disciplines and how they interact (Billingsley et al, 2018). The various different methods and approaches within psychology can be roughly categorized into two epistemic schools: Psychology as a natural science and psychological humanities (Morf, 2018; Sugarman & Martin, 2020). While psychology as a natural science follows the classic scientific-positivist paradigm, the psychological humanities mostly concern themselves with the study of subjective experience (Teo, 2017). This article makes the case that other disciplines would profit from an increased interdisciplinary exchange with psychology, as shown by examples within the natural sciences and the humanities. This inter-disciplinary communication of different epistemic schools can help us discover new knowledge transcending any one approach to research, while also forming and solidifying the unique identity psychology has as a subject between natural sciences and the humanities.

The Identity of Psychology as a Discipline

The position psychology inhabits within the scientific community is to some extent owned to the subject area it is trying to investigate. Historically speaking, psychological thought was part and parcel of many philosophical traditions. In antiquity, Aristotle discussed the parts and workings of the soul and its different modes of interaction with the environment (Matthews, 2003). And the medieval scholastic Thomas of Aquin discussed how habits and automatization in behaviour can occur (Castiello, 1936). However, psychology wasn't structurally differentiated from other disciplines until the mid-1850s.

Psychology is commonly defined as the scientific study of mind and behaviour (Gross, 2012), although this definition is not without controversy. The notion of mind is in part derived from a dualistic conception of reality (Stich & Warfield, 2008), posing the existence of a separate nonphysical substance that the mind is made of. This notion of a dualistic reality concept would be disregarded by a positivistic-scientific understanding, due to its unfalsifiable nature.

Furthermore, the mind is conceptually grounded within the subjective experience of each individual. This makes it inherently difficult to study through objective methodologies, given objective methodologies want to specifically exclude the subjective aspects of knowledge. One attempt to resolve this dilemma of studying subjective experience with objective means can be found in the cognitive revolution starting in the 1950s (Miller, 2003). Cognitive-psychologists treated the mind as analogous to a computer, being composed of sub-components such as memory and processor. This description of symbolic metaphors, in cognitive psychology with the mind as a computer, allowed for a scientific investigation of psychological processes, based on the presupposition that the metaphors used are somewhat accurately describing the workings of the objectively unapproachable mind. However, the cognitive approach is only one among many, giving the discipline its flexibility.

The “bridging” position psychology inhabits between different academic disciplines makes it a fruitful subject for interdisciplinary research, given that psychology is not limited to a single ontological school within the sciences (Sewell, 1989; Skala, 2008). In other words, psychological concepts can be used in a variety of different disciplines, because psychology itself is very variable. Psychology has always been a subject of interdisciplinary importance, given that by its very nature it deals with a multitude of human phenomena (Epstein, 2014). However, this article argues that there are multiple areas of research that could benefit by including epistemic insights generated through psychological concepts.

Artificial Intelligence and Psychology

One area that could benefit from reintroducing psychological concepts could be artificial intelligence research. A clearcut definition of artificial intelligence is difficult to find, given the broadness and complexity of this area of investigation. Roughly speaking, artificial intelligence concerns itself with things, in current research mainly computer programs, imitating intelligent human behaviour (Kok et al, 2009). The study of artificial intelligence has many overlaps with natural scientific components of psychology. These are found at the intersection of artificial intelligence, cognitive psychology and neuroscience. Neuroscience concerns itself with the modelling and understanding of the central nervous system.

Given that the modelling of artificial intelligence aims towards the imitation of intelligent human behaviour, one can understand why an area of interest could be the very subject, the central nervous system, artificial intelligence is trying to model. Therefore, the historical and recent intersections between artificial intelligence, cognitive psychology and neuroscience seem self-evident (Hassabis et al, 2017). This is less the case if one looks at intersections between artificial intelligence research and concepts and topics from the psychological humanities.

However, the consideration of subjective experience in artificial intelligence research is becoming relevant rather quickly. If the imitation of human intelligent behaviour through artificial agents becomes so very detailed that we cannot differentiate whether or not the artificial agent has its own subjective experience or not, there needs to be an account of how we treat those artificial agents. Even though this line of argumentation sounds much like science fiction, some researchers seem to think that the moment artificial intelligence will have subjective experience is not far. For example, the neuropsychologist Mark Solms outlines in his book the hidden spring that the sum of homeostasis-oriented feedback-systems underlying human-information-processing creates subjective experience due to their hierarchical organization and communication within the central nervous system (Solms, 2021; Solms & Friston, 2018).

If this is the case, subjective experience will become a product once a certain threshold of complexity in an artificial intelligence is reached. In other words, if one puts together a clutch, a differential, an input shaft and a multitude of other parts in the right order, at a certain level the result of the various parts configured together will emerge as a gear-box.

If an artificial agent develops subjective experience, or more conservatively, if it becomes so good at imitating it that there is no way to differentiate the two anymore, some very important questions arise as to how such an “artificial being” should be treated. Given, as already outlined, that artificial intelligence development draws to substantial parts from neuroscientific knowledge, psychological concepts about subjective experience could prove very useful in understanding the artificial agent’s behaviour and accommodate its needs. Notions of psychological interventions such as cognitive behaviour therapy for example could be applied and adjusted to artificial agents. To overstate the case somewhat, artificial agents of the future might need a psychologist to help them make sense of everything going on with them.

Similarly, the psychological implications for humans when interacting with artificial intelligence need to be taken into account. Machine learning and inference-algorithms are already used and relevant in everyday life. Domains like social-media, search engines like google, or even just the very basic interface of one’s smart phone draw on knowledge generated through machine learning (Balaji et al, 2021). These interactions have undoubtedly had a significant influence on our mental life (Sundar, 2020). Therefore, knowledge about our psychological predispositions should be considered when designing artificial machines that are made to interact with us. This could be vital to reduce risk of various well-being issues, such as for example psychological dependence. Even though psychological concepts have been widely considered in the design of social media platforms and smart phone interfaces (Fox, 2018), there is room for considering factors that contribute to the psychological well-being of users. This investigation into overlapping topics between artificial intelligence and subjective experience shows one aspect of what psychology as a discipline has to offer to this scientific inquiry. These types of interdisciplinary exchanges provide an invaluable point of contact for all those involved creating the type of dialogue that informs and develops research in fruitful directions; Using the language of ‘Epistemic Insight’ such points of contact, helps to facilitate insightful thinking towards gaining a deeper understanding.

Political Science and Biopsychology

Another area psychological concepts could be increasingly helpful with are the social sciences. Social Sciences, such as Political Science, Anthropology and Sociology, generally lean more towards the humanities end of the academia-spectrum. If Social Scientists work empirical, they generally utilize surveys, questionnaires as well as statistics about trends to gain knowledge about processes occurring within societies. There is a part of psychology, called social psychology, that exists in close entanglement with other social sciences, such as sociology or political science (Karpf, 1932).

However, the social sciences haven’t really utilised knowledge generated through psychobiological research about the biological substructure underlying social events. Kihlstrom (2010) argues so far as to say that the reduction of social sciences to social neuroscience threatens the independent existence of social sciences in general, by reducing the subjectiveness of social phenomena into the objective. He considers this a potential problem of involving natural-scientific knowledge into social phenomena. While this point definitely has a lot of truth to it, social interactions don’t exist reclusive and independent of the biological substrate out of which they emerge. Biological knowledge about psychological predispositions could thereby provide vital information necessary for understanding a wide array of social phenomena. This line of argument for example brought forward by Weingart et al (2013), who argue that the appropriate place for the study of human culture is located between biology and the social sciences.

This area of inter-disciplinary investigation between biology and the social sciences could become increasingly relevant, considering the significant advances that psychobiological approaches, like neuroscience and evolutionary psychology, have made in explaining the biological substructure underlying patterns of social-behaviour in humans (Moskowitz, 2018).

For example, one area of research that could help in understanding the social-scientific phenomenon of political polarization are neuropsychological measurements of attention. Political polarization has been a focus of social scientific research for a while now, particularly regarding its relation to social media (Tucker et al, 2018). The neuropsychological concept of attention could help shed light on mechanisms occurring within the psyche when an individual's attitudes become polarized.

While, according to William James, "everybody knows what attention is", it is actually very difficult to define. This is partly because attention doesn't refer to a single phenomenon but is already a multitude of distinct processes in itself (Style, 2006). Nevertheless, attention is generally described as the spotlight of the mind, focusing on a very narrow set of events, while excluding a multitude of others. Attention can be researched through a variety of different neuropsychological tests and neuroimaging techniques, for example Stroop's task (Williams et al, 1996). Attentional biases have been linked to a variety of psychopathologies, including anxiety disorders (Bradley et al, 1999), schizophrenia (Moritz & Laudan, 2007) and depression (Mennen et al, 2019).

Neuropsychological tests could provide vital insights into attentional biases underlying the political polarization of individuals. By understanding the neural mechanisms underlying our social dialogue we could reduce political polarization and foster understanding between people. After all, one could hypothesize that one of the reasons people with different political opinions have difficulty in engaging in knowledge exchange is that they are attending to radically different occurrences within the environment.

A Conclusion: Psychology and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Why should intra- or interdisciplinary approaches be a goal? Why shouldn't scientific disciplines strictly adhere to the complexities within their own subject area, given that there is no shortage of complexities there? This article claims that even though one can lose oneself in the infinite-seeming complexity of a specific subject area, inter-disciplinary exchange is vital if science wants to not only increase subject-specific knowledge, but to be able to actually integrate a multitude of different approaches and form cohesive strategies regarding the direction which human development should take. This article wanted to demonstrate that psychology, due to its peculiar position within academia, has the potential to further our understanding of natural-scientific inquiry through the re-introduction of subjective experience into the various natural-science disciplines, for example concerning future interactions with artificial agents. Similarly, psychology through interdisciplinary exchanges can help inform the humanities about the biological substrate subjective experience is built upon, as in the example outlined regarding potential neuropsychological mechanisms driving social phenomena such as political polarization. Psychology can therefore help those two schools of thought within academia to communicate with each other and develop interdisciplinary dialogue, as the German saying goes, "den Wald vor lauter Bäumen wieder zu sehen" (to once more see the forest with all those trees in the way).

References

- Balaji, T. K. et al (2021). Machine learning algorithms for social media analysis: A survey. *Computer Science Review*, 40, 100395.
- Barsalou, L. W. (2014). *Cognitive psychology: An overview for cognitive scientists*. Psychology Press.
- Billingsley, B. et al (2018). "A Framework for Teaching Epistemic Insight in Schools". *Research in Science Education*. 48 (6): 1115–1131.
- Bradley, B. P. et al (1999). Attentional bias for emotional faces in generalized anxiety disorder. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 38(3), 267-278.
- Castiello, J. (1936). The psychology of habit in St. Thomas Aquinas. *The Modern Schoolman*, 14(1), 8-12.
- Durrheim, K. (1997). Social constructionism, discourse, and psychology. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 27(3), 175-182.
- Epstein, S. L. (2014). Making interdisciplinary collaboration work. In *Interdisciplinary collaboration* (pp. 265-284). Psychology Press.
- Fox, J. (2018). An unlikeable truth: Social media like buttons are designed to be addictive. They're impacting our ability to think rationally. *Index on Censorship*, 47(3), 11-13
- Friston, K. et al (2016). Active inference and learning. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 68, 862-879.
- Gross, R. (2012). *Psychology: The science of mind and behaviour 6th Edition*. Hachette UK.
- Hassabis, D. et al (2017). Neuroscience-inspired artificial intelligence. *Neuron*, 95(2), 245-258.
- Kalat, J. W. (2015). *Biological psychology*. Cengage Learning.
- Karpf, F. B. (1932). American social psychology: Its origins, development, and European background.
- Kihlstrom, J. F. (2010). Social neuroscience: the footprints of Phineas Gage. *Social Cognition*, 28(6), 757.
- Kok, J. N. et al (2009). Artificial intelligence: definition, trends, techniques, and cases. *Artificial intelligence*, 1, 270-299.
- Mennen, A. C., Norman, K. A., & Turk-Browne, N. B. (2019). Attentional bias in depression: understanding mechanisms to improve training and treatment. *Current opinion in psychology*, 29, 266-273.
- Miller, G. A. (2003). The cognitive revolution: a historical perspective. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 7(3), 141-144.
- Morf, M. E. (2018). Agency Chance, and the scientific status of psychology. *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 52(4), 491–507.
- Moritz, S., & Laudan, A. (2007). Attention bias for paranoia-relevant visual stimuli in schizophrenia. *Cognitive Neuropsychiatry*, 12(5), 381-390.
- Moskowitz, M. (2018). *Reading minds: A guide to the cognitive neuroscience revolution*. Routledge.
- Matthews, G. (2003). Aristotle: Psychology. *The Blackwell Guide to*, 211.
- Sewell, W. H. (1989). Some reflections on the golden age of interdisciplinary social psychology. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 15(1), 1-17.
- Skala, D. (2008). Overconfidence in psychology and finance-an interdisciplinary literature review. *Bank i kredyt*, (4), 33-50.

- Solms, M., & Friston, K. (2018). How and why consciousness arises: some considerations from physics and physiology. *Journal of Consciousness Studies*, 25(5-6), 202-238.
- Solms, M. (2021). *The hidden spring: A journey to the source of consciousness*. Profile books.
- Spiegelberg, H., & Murray, E. L. (1973). Phenomenology in psychology and psychiatry. *Journal of Phenomenological Psychology*, 4(1), 375-379.
- Stich, S. P., & Warfield, T. A. (2008). *The Blackwell guide to philosophy of mind*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Styles, E. (2006). *The psychology of attention*. Psychology Press.
- Sugarman, J., & Martin, J. (Eds.). (2020). *A humanities approach to the psychology of personhood*. Routledge.
- Sundar, S. S. (2020). Rise of machine agency: A framework for studying the psychology of human–AI interaction (HAI). *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 25(1), 74-88.
- Teo, T. (2017). From psychological science to the psychological humanities: Building a general theory of subjectivity. *Review of General Psychology*, 21(4), 281-291.
- Tucker, J. A. et al (2018). Social media, political polarization, and political disinformation: A review of the scientific literature. *Political polarization, and political disinformation: a review of the scientific literature* (March 19, 2018).
- Weingart, P. et al (2013). *Human by nature: Between biology and the social sciences*. Psychology Press.
- Wieczorek, O., Unger, S., Riebling, J., Erhard, L., Koß, C., & Heiberger, R. (2021). Mapping the field of psychology: Trends in research topics 1995–2015. *Scientometrics*, 126(12), 9699-9731.
- Williams, J. M. G. et al (1996). The emotional Stroop task and psychopathology. *Psychological bulletin*, 120(1), 3.
- Yanchar, S. C., & Hill, J. R. (2003). What is psychology about? Toward an explicit ontology. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 43(1), 11-32.

PRACTICAL'S PLACE IN PEDAGOGY: IGNITING A PASSION FOR SCIENCE

Angus Hope

Abstract

Practical has the capacity to really ignite a student's passion for science. Sometimes the fire lights but the flames splutter, leaving only a few fading embers. But other times with a little more oxygen and kindling it sparks a blaze that burns for a lifetime. This article delves into how practical can improve student engagement with science at secondary school level, and how it helps develop an understanding through which scientific knowledge is achieved. Arguably, the current science curriculum generates a tension between the need to deliver content for assessment, and engaging students with tangible scientific problems; this informs current debate about effective pedagogies for learning science.

When students are quizzed about what they do in science lessons at secondary school, a common response is "err... practicals!". This is especially true when considering Chemistry and Physics, which boast the most 'obvious' practicals. Considering that the subject matter of science is the corporeal world, it should seem apparent and natural, that understanding science should involve seeing and manipulating perceptible materials. The Department of Education has their own take on practical and its place in learning science. Practical science delivered with flair and knowledge can help pupils understand scientific concepts and ignite their interest in Physics, Chemistry, and Biology. *Practical science is also an important part of scientific knowledge and teaches pupils about the empirical basis of scientific enquiry.* (Department for Education, 2011). Effective practical are those experiments which use unambiguous and deliberate techniques of 'scaffolding' an individual students' reasoning. They are able to direct and channel their thinking and passion along creative lines.

A place in pedagogy: The debate of effectiveness

The notion of the 'effectiveness' of a given teaching and learning practical has been thrown around the scientific education community for some time and must be carefully considered before utilising a given activity. It may be beneficial to clarify what I mean by the idea of 'effectiveness'. Figure 1 shows four stages in the development and implementation of a teaching activity task. The effectiveness of a given practical goes through two checkpoints. The first checkpoint is: are the students able to conduct what the teacher intends them to do? There needs to be a match between what we intend students to do and see and what they actually do and see. This is about the relationship between B and C in Figure 1. This relationship is labelled 'effectiveness (1)'. Yet when teachers talk about the effectiveness of a practical task, they mean the extent to which it helps students to learn what we want them to learn. This is checkpoint two and details the relationship between A and D in Figure 1. This is labelled 'effectiveness (2)'. It is by far no easy task to quantify or assess. The teacher would first need to decide if they were interested in evidence of learning in the short term or in the long term. It should be recognised that when learning does occur, it is probably the result of a series of lessons of which a practical activity is just one part. Providing students with a detailed protocol usually reflects the teacher's initial reservation of not being able to achieve 'effectiveness (1)', whilst taking away the value of the practical activity in terms of 'effectiveness (2)'. This is currently a common criticism of practical teaching in the lab. That the practical work becomes more akin to following a recipe and forgoing the students need to think about their actions and why they are doing them.

Figure 1: The stages in the development and evaluation of a teaching and learning practical activity and its relationship to two measures of effectiveness. (Millar and Abrahams 2009)

The development and effectiveness evaluation model of practicals shown in Figure 1 was originally created by the European Labwork in Science Education project (Millar, Tiberghien and Le Maréchal, 2002). However, effectiveness is sometimes measured by its ability to allow a student to delve into the subject and garner greater interest.

Passion: Student engagement using practicals

One study published by Abrahams in 2009 puts it forward that what teaching professionals consider and identify as 'motivation' has suggested that "what teachers frequently refer to as 'motivation' is, in a strict psychological sense, better understood as 'situational interest'" (Abrahams 2009). Given that situational interest, compared to personal interest, rarely persists beyond the end of single science lesson, (Hidi and Harackiewicz, 2000) this provides an explanation as to why pupils need to be repeatedly re-stimulated by the frequent use of practicals. If teachers are able to appreciate that difference between motivation or personal interest, and situational interest then they can create meaningful practical tasks. There are students who claim to appreciate practical science lessons, even though these same students

have little interest in the subject or intention of pursuing science post compulsion. Their reasons for enjoying practical work appear to be primarily that they see it as preferable to non-practical teaching techniques that they associate with more writing (Hodson, 1990). From teaching at my own school and discussing with teaching professionals and educationalists, it would seem that within a student's first year at secondary school, the novelty of being in a laboratory environment appears to wear off and they evidently become disillusioned by the reality of school science, which is clearly very different from the image that teachers initially seek to create in order to make their subject appear attractive on, for example, Open Days or A Level Options evenings.

Erduran et. al. (2021) comments on motivation and student perception within science. Interest in any given subject and the enjoyment experienced from it are underlined by self-determinate and intrinsic forms of motivation, to learn the subject in question works in tandem with this. Intrinsic motivation affects the extent of student engagement and performance. Usually, this level of interest correlates with academic performance and this correlation manifests itself most evidently with the three sciences. One student will gravitate towards a single type of motivation compared to others. In order to motivate the majority of the classroom at every interval, the motivation will need to be varied each time.

In my own experience as a teacher, what stimulates student engagement or curiosity ahead of a practical is the challenge. I have given a class of Year 10 chemistry students samples of similar appearing solutions and asked them to identify them. I have posed a problem for them to solve. I have already taught them chemical analysis tests and safe procedures for both anions and cations, and provided suitable equipment in the lab without physically putting the 'correct' equipment in front

of them but otherwise let them get from A to B. The students are then able to step up and think 'What do I need to use to find out what is in each solution?', or 'Can I use one test for validating multiple different ions?'. I encouraged what is termed as epistemic curiosity, "the desire to obtain new knowledge" (Litman, 2012). This epistemic curiosity is a motivation tool for practical science and provides an opportunity for students to begin to gain epistemic insight. After the practical I then reviewed what they discovered and tested them to gain a measure of their understanding and what they gained from the practical. From this assessment I set up another practical the following week. This time, the same class were asked to separate a mixture of solids and solutions. Again, I provided them with suitable equipment available in the lab and the mixtures themselves and asked them to separate the constituent substances. The students were able to apply this epistemic insight, or 'knowledge about scholarly thinking' to this new problem and the initial motivation of the problem to be solved. Epistemic insight encourages students to reflect on the power, relevance, and limitations of science. Billingsley and Nassaji (2017) comment on how science relates to other areas of scholarship and understanding by using are questions that bridge subject boundaries which would potentially pique a student's interest and curiosity into a given part of practical in science, and why we are completing it in class. My learning objectives for each of the two practical lessons were to assess their understanding of chemical tests and what things did the students need to find out to find the solution. Both of which I asked as part of my review and each time I was pleased with the response. This may be an avenue for assessment of practical science that could be explored in the future.

Sshana and Abulibdeh (2020) identify a positive correlation between pupil progress and use of practicals. The reported findings are further supported by a study by Abdi (2014), which stated that the experimental groups showed increased academic attainment and a greater understanding of content covered, notably true regarding questions that required interpretation and retrieval. Hodson (1990) considered that practical work can motivate students and stimulate their passion in scientific learning.

Most recently, I conducted a required practical investigation for an A Level Chemistry class based on calibration curves and half neutralization point of a weak acid with a strong base. I altered the experiment so it allowed the students to select appropriate glassware that would allow them to most accurately accrue the data required and construct a graph to work out an experimental pKa and subsequent Ka (acid dissociation constant) of the weak acid. My scaffolding for this investigation was that they would have to complete at least one titration and calibrate a pH meter as well as circulating the room to assist with instrumental and experimental misunderstandings. I challenged the students to make decisions in equipment and how to go about collecting a pH of a half neutralization point. From this practical, each student had to submit their calibration curve, an experimental Ka for the weak acid and a calculated percentage accuracy from a given literature value of said weak acid's Ka. I concluded that giving the choice of choosing equipment forced students to think about how they would go about this task. From a google form questionnaire and conversations with each student afterwards, they reported that they understood the need for a calibration curve and how experimental results can differ from quoted literature. The three classes trialed also reported an enjoyment of the challenge of the more open-ended and less hand holding recipe style practical.

Contrary to these positive implications, Boyuk et. al. (2010) have reported that teachers have reservations when considering completing practical activities. These teachers appreciated that lab-based activities are a core aspect of learning the sciences, but reoccurring issues were encountered. "Such as the lack of materials needed for the required experiment: insufficient information for carrying out the experiment or the techniques it requires; insufficient glassware and or chemicals; a lack of health and safety provision; a lack of understanding of the steps needed to avoid accidents, and finally, not knowing what to do in case of an accident during the experiment." (Boyuk et. al., 2010)

Conclusions

In terms of engagement, there are two distinct reasons why students' perceptions and passion of practical work in the three sciences as they progress through secondary school. The first of which is, as the perceived intellectual challenge of chemistry, physics, and biology becomes more demanding, the more students welcome the 'break' of practical work and allows them to avoid thinking scientifically. The second is when the student becomes more cognisant of the importance of developing their theoretical understanding and problem solving compared with engaging and enjoying a practical activity. Sharpe (2015) commented on this very understanding. For example, by Year 10, where students feel lessons to be more driven by GCSE examination requirements, they begin to see practical work as being less effective in their learning when compared to other methods of teaching. Teachers need to be more aware that practical work generates substantial enthusiasm in all three science subjects at Key Stage 3 (KS3) but that this enthusiasm declines as students move into and through Key Stage 4 (KS4). Such an awareness might therefore suggest that having more practical work in KS3, as a means of further engaging students with school science, might be beneficial, before reducing it to the current level in KS4 but utilising practical is a more focused learning capacity so as to enable students to concentrate more effectively on achieving desired examination results.

In this very article I have discussed parameters of effectiveness and some of my own practicals I have instructed. Upon my own research-informed reflection having completed this article. I would apply Abraham and Millar's model of practical effectiveness to my own practicals. Ensuring that I strive for both measures of effectiveness whilst drawing out epistemic curiosity within students. Enhancing and cultivating epistemic insight could be a great part into what makes that effective pedagogy for science. This would allow the students to gain a greater insight into the processes rather than learning the material for examinations. If a practical is going to be worth their weight in terms of their performing enhancing and engagement capabilities, I myself as the teacher must be crystal clear on what I am using the practical for. A practical task should have a limited number of intended learning outcomes. It is easy for practical tasks to become overcomplicated to the point at which students get lost in the 'noise' of the lab bench. If a specific skill is necessary for a task, students need to be competent in this beforehand, or it may get in the way of the intended learning. For example, if the teacher wants a class to measure resistance at different points in a parallel circuit with a variety of components, they must first be competent in building a circuit to match a given diagram, and in using a voltmeter and an ammeter to calculate the resistance. It is better to establish these competencies in advance than to believe they can be picked up in the course of a more complex activity. And, in the case of practical tasks which require the students to make links between the domain of objects and observables (things or properties that we can see directly) and the domain of ideas (the unseen or unobservable entities and behaviours). This, and the extent of engagement, are fundamental behind the purpose of practical.

References

Department for Education (2011) Written Evidence Submitted by the Department for Education to the House of Lords Science and Technology Committee

Millar, R., Abrahams, I. (2009), Practical work: making it more effective, *School Science Review*, 91(334), 59-64.

Millar, R., Tiberghien, A., Le Maréchal, JF. (2002), Varieties of Labwork: A Way of Profiling Labwork Tasks. In: Psillos, D., Niedderer, H. (eds) *Teaching and Learning in the Science Laboratory*, 16, 9-20

Abrahams, I. (2009), Does practical work really motivate? A study of the affective value of practical work in secondary school science, *International Journal of Science Education*, 31 (17), 2335-2353.

- El Masri Y. H., Erdruan S., Ioannidou O. (2021), Designing practical science assessments in England: students' engagement and perceptions, *Research in Science & Technological Education*.
- Litman, J. A. (2012), Epistemic Curiosity, *Encyclopedia of the Science of Learning*, Springer, Boston, MA
- Billingsley B., Nassaji M., 2017, Ways to Develop Students' Appreciation of the Power and Limitations of Science, in Gillian Straine (ed), *Are There Limits to Science?*, 1st Edition, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne, 154-165.
- Sshana, Z.J., & Abulibdeh, E.S. (2020), Science practical work and its impact on students' science achievement, *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 10(2), 199-215.
- Abdi, A. (2014), The Effect of Inquiry-based Learning Method on Students' Academic Achievement in Science Course, *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 2(1),37-41.
- Hodson, D. (1990). A critical look at practical work in school science, *School Science Review*, 70(256), 33-40.
- Boyuk, U., Demir, S., & Erol, M. (2010), Analysing the proficiency views of science and Technology teachers on laboratory studies in terms of different variables, *TUBAV Bilim Dergisi*, 3(4), 342-349.
- Sharpe, R (2015), Students' attitudes to practical work by age and subject, *School Review*, 357, 25-36.

Epistemic Insight

How do we solve the
Big Questions,
opportunities and
problems of today
and tomorrow?

**The problem
loneliness**

What about if uni students from different disciplines could form a group and tackle these challenges together. Why don't we do more of that?

FIND OUT MORE AT
[futureofknowledge.com](http://futureofknowledge.com/knowledge-labs)
[/knowledge-labs](https://www.facebook.com/knowledge-labs)

 Canterbury
Christ Church
University

CO-CREATION DURING A LASAR WORK PLACEMENT

Buffy-Lucy Jennings

While on placement with the LASAR (Learning about Science and Religion) Research Centre I worked with experienced researchers on a project to test one of the tools that are in the Epistemic Insight toolbox. Epistemic insight means knowledge about knowledge – and this project tested the value of the Epistemic Insight Discipline Wheel as a tool to help us to address the question of ‘what is the nature of friendship?’. Other areas of work where I contributed to during the placement included inputting and discussing data gathered via surveys in schools.

Monday 11th April 2022

This was the first day of when the placement began.

After introductions and discussing project outlines, we focused on a new area of work for LASAR – testing the value of the Discipline Wheel as a tool for use in Higher Education. The aim of the study was to explore its potential to help HE students to build their understanding of their own and other disciplines and how disciplines can work together. As such, it is an example of what is called a ‘co-creation research project’ where the students and course designers collaborate to develop and evaluate a teaching resource.

The Epistemic Insight Discipline wheel was important in the researching because it showed each of the disciplines that we could examine and work on individually. The Epistemic Insight wheel that we used for the question of ‘what is the nature of friendship?’ contained ten subjects and each one linked to friendship. However, this was not as simple as I first thought it would be because myself and the person I worked with struggled to find scholarly information about friendship for our set disciplines. For example, I worked on finding about the nature of friendship in the discipline English. As a student doing an English degree, I figured the best place to start would be there, but it was a struggle to find anything about friendship related to English. I had this trouble with the other disciplines I worked on too, but I decided to consider famous friendships within novels, stories, and other literature. This became a useful skill for me because it was an easier way to find out relevant information about friendship.

The project team and I co-created what was the best way to approach it and chose to divide it up so that we were each working on different subjects. The ten subjects included, English, The Arts, Philosophy, Computer Science, Mathematics, Science, Psychology (originally Economics), Geography, History, and Theology, Religious Studies. I worked on English, The Arts, Science and Psychology. We then discussed how we wished to present our work and decided it would be in the form of a poster. The project team and I each researched scholarly sources that were related to friendship in each discipline. The discipline wheel is useful for answering a question such as ‘what is the nature of friendship’ because people can think and consider how other disciplines can answer the question. For example, a student with a degree in English may answer that friendship can be based on who you trust. Shakespeare shows this with the friendship between Hamlet and Horatio, not on class status or interests, whereas, a mathematics student may view friendship in the form of one person inviting n amount of friends to a party and within that party, each person will know another person. (Longyear, Parsons, 1972)

In deciding how we would split up the disciplines on the EI discipline wheel, the project team agreed that I would take on English, The Arts, Science and Psychology and the other person would do Philosophy, Computer Science, History, and Theology, Religious Studies. Mathematics was given to one of the team members from LASAR and both of us did some research for Geography.

After discussing the project outlines, and co-creating the disciplines, for the rest of the day we worked on a spreadsheet containing survey data and helped organise it. Using the data, I was given, I had to match up the data that was on one spreadsheet to another spreadsheet. To maximise workload we switched it around, so that one of us was doing the spreadsheet and the other was working on and conducting research for the friendship project.

**Student Name: Buffy
Lucy Jennings
Period of Placement
(start and end date):
11.04.22-17.04.22**

**Organisation (placement
provider): LASAR**

Pre-Placement Section

Post-Placement Section: Partner Debrief

To be completed at end of the placement		
Proposed Activities on Placement	Outcomes	Comments from Placement Provider
1. Research and develop a profile of friendship using an EI discipline wheel	completed	A well-researched profile of friendship was created.
2. Work with EI survey/research data and help collate an Excel spreadsheet	completed	Valuable input on organising an excel spreadsheet of survey data.
3. Help propose ways an ERD profile of loneliness can be created.	completed	Discussed and preliminary research conducted.
Student Signature: Buffy-Lucy Jennings	Student Signature: Buffy-Lucy Jennings	
Provider Signature: Aryn Litchfield	Provider Signature: Aryn Litchfield	
Date: 11.04.22	Date: 17.04.22	

Fig 1: Proposed activities that were discussed during the LASAR work placement.

Tuesday 12th April 2022

The project team and I worked on the survey spreadsheets before switching over to our main project. The spreadsheet was a challenge at first but the more familiar I become with the data the more expedient I became at organising it.

After a break, we turned our attention to working on the friendship discipline wheel. Firstly, we started to research information about loneliness for the bubble tool project, but we mostly came up with the same ideas and information we found. With the discipline wheel, we had to decide how we wanted to present it. It was decided by the project team that it would be in poster form.

I worked on trying to find scholarly information about the disciplines I was tasked with. I began with English because I thought it would be the best place to start. However, this was not as easy as I thought it would be because I struggled to find information relating friendship and English together. This posed a dilemma for me, and I had to think of another way to get my research. I decided to consider famous friendship within literatures of English. I started with a friendship from a well-known Shakespeare play, Hamlet. Doing this allowed me to get quotes about friendship and consider the friendships of the playwright. I did this with other forms of literature, and it proved to be effective because it opened up more ways for me to research how English and friendship can be linked.

Fig 2: Epistemic insight discipline wheel we used for the project on friendship (left). Epistemic insight bubble tool we used for exploratory research on loneliness (right)

Wednesday 13th April 2022

Today, the project team and I finished the survey spreadsheets and continued the discipline wheel.

Spreadsheet done, I continued working on the friendship discipline wheel. For the rest of the day I tried to find out scholarly information for the other disciplines. Firstly, I added some more information to the English discipline before moving onto the next discipline, The Arts. As I was researching about friendship within The Arts, I realised that the term was too broad which made this more difficult for me. Like with English, I had to find a way to work around the term.

In order to find information on The Arts as a whole, I decided to consider what The Arts are. For example, I thought about the various sub-genres that The Arts contained such as music, songs, plays, and a few others. This proved to be effective because it allowed me to expand on my research of scholarly quotes about friendship. For example, friendship can be shown within musical interests, 'Art can be shared between friends influencing styles and facilitating exposure to new forms of creativity. In times of struggle "art approaches, as a saving and healing enchantress."' (Selfhout, et al. 2009).

Once I had managed to find some scholarly quotes and research on The Arts, I moved onto the next discipline I was tasked with, Science. As I was researching about friendship within Science, I realised I had the same issue with finding information. I tried searching up scientists and seeing how their friendships impacted them. For example, I found out about friendships between Einstein and Besso and Locke and Newton. Using this, I found information about the relationship between each of these friends such as 'in 1897 Anna, the oldest of the Winteler daughters, visited Zurich, and Einstein made a major contribution to Besso's life by introducing her to him' (Medicus, 1994). This is showing that friendship within chemistry has the ability or inability to affect personal relations which can be influential to someone in science.

Thursday 14th April 2022

Our aim was to get the research for the discipline wheel completed today.

Although today was slightly different because we were working remotely and therefore communicated through Teams. On Teams we discussed with one of the team members from LASAR about how

the project was going and whether the project team would be able to finish it by the deadline. The deadline given for the friendship discipline wheel was by the end of today (14th April).

I continued to work on finishing the research that I was doing, however, I had to redo some of the research because I was unable to access my work. This made it more challenging to get the research done by the deadline. Fortunately, I was able to find most of the research I had previously gotten and added some other scholarly research to it.

Fig 3: My research notes on friendship.

Tuesday 19th April 2022

This was the final day of the placement. On this day, the project team and I finished off our friendship discipline project and discussed about how we were going to have our work presented.

We chose to stick with the poster idea deciding to have small bits of information along the side explaining in more detail and what the research means. There would also be an interactive discipline wheel where you click on one of the disciplines and after reading it, you can move onto the next one (as shown in fig 4).

The project team also did consider linking each of the disciplines to another discipline because some overlapped. However, as we had a deadline, we instead chose not to do this and just focused on getting completing the poster.

Asking ourselves the question of 'what is the nature of friendship,' lead towards us having multiple definitions of what friendship is defined as. This meant that we needed to find and research information for each discipline that could explain the nature of friendship. Using the EI discipline wheel, the project team split up each of the discipline and conducted research into the set disciplines. Using this process allowed me to understand that different disciplines have something valuable to offer. For example, it showed me that some people in the discipline of English may see friendship as a form of entertainment and trust. On the other hand, people in the discipline of philosophy such as Aristotle see friendship in "three ways – formed for pleasure and satisfaction, formed for utility on usefulness and formed for virtuous on appreciation of morals" (Aristotle, 1984) This showed me that anything can be put in the middle of the discipline wheel, and everyone will have their own view on the term.

CAN ANY SINGULAR PERSPECTIVE SUM UP A DISCIPLINE?

This was the puzzle LASAR Centre asked us to solve and this is our journey:

Our research was conducted through academic journals, Google scholar, and library resources at CCCU. As a group we decided to divide the curricular disciplines on the wheel randomly between each-other, and while this provided the opportunity for us to do our research individually, we frequently regrouped to discuss our findings and research to determine if we were on the right track.

Initially we posed a simple question at each discipline, namely: "what is the nature of friendship in the context of 'X'?". However, this led us to gaining a lot of content knowledge but not necessarily a critical perspective, i.e. did the research we uncover actually provide a robust answer? It seemed like something was missing in the process, as it became clear that content itself did not provide critical insight. The further we delved into each discipline, the more apparent it became that a singular perspective was insufficient, as there were just too many pieces of the puzzle. For example, in The Arts we discovered rich conversations surrounding the idea that friendship selection amongst peer groups was influenced by shared artistic preferences. However, in other areas of research, art was described as a healing enchantress or a friend in times of struggle. Which perspective was the one that best reflected the nature of friendship in the context of the arts? Both seemed to be equally valid perspectives. Each discipline was replete with similar examples, even ones we initially thought would have limited things to say about friendship.

The discipline wheel we have completed represents not so much our attempt to answer the puzzle, but rather, to demonstrate our critical perspective from interacting with the research, and to leave some of 'the bread crumbs' of our journey behind.

Buffy & Liam

Fig 4: project output - Interactive discipline wheel and reflection. Available at: <https://www.epistemicinsight.com/can-any-singular-perspective-sum-up-a-discipline/>

The question of 'what is the nature of friendship' can be answered by a single discipline because each one has their own opinion of friendship. However, despite the question being possible to answer with a single discipline, it works better when every person researching about friendship has their own opinions. When considering friendship as a topic, people will have their own ideas and each person's idea is a valid one because each person researching a discipline can understand where another is coming from. All the disciplines interact with another in one or more ways. The EI discipline wheel process was helpful in recognising the importance of interdisciplinary perspectives because it gave me an insight into how friendship can be seen different depending on a person's perspective.

References:

Aristotle (1984) *Nicomachean Ethics*, Edited by: L. Brown. Translated by: D. Ross. New York: Books Publishing.

LASAR (Learning about Science and Religion), "THE EPISTEMIC INSIGHT FRAMEWORK FOR KEY STAGE 3." <http://epistemicinsight.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/epistemic-insight-for-KS3-July19.pdf> pp. 12-13.

Longyear, J. Q., Parsons, T. D (1972) 'The Friendship Theorem'. *Elsevier*, Vol 75, 3, pp.257-262

Jennings, Buffy-Lucy – LASAR 2022 PLACEMENT DOCUMENTATION, page 3.

Medicus, H. A, (1994) "The friendship among three singular men: Einstein and his Swiss friends Besso and Zangger." *Isis* 85.3 456-478.

Selfhout, M, H, W, et al. (2009) "The role of music preferences in early adolescents' friendship formation and stability." *Journal of adolescence* 32.1, 95-107.

Epistemic Insight

How do we solve the **Big Questions, opportunities and problems** of today and tomorrow?

What about if uni students from different disciplines could form a group and tackle these challenges together. Why don't we do more of that?

FIND OUT MORE AT
[futureofknowledge.com](http://futureofknowledge.com/knowledge-labs)
[/knowledge-labs](https://www.facebook.com/knowledge-labs)

 Canterbury
Christ Church
University

EI STUDENTS IN RESEARCH: RESEARCH PLACEMENTS AT THE LASAR CENTRE

Aryn Litchfield

Introduction

The LASAR Centre is committed to developing a research culture that champions multidisciplinary conversations at all stages within academia and beyond. We are keen to develop opportunities for co-creation, knowledge generation, and knowledge exchange that allow critical insight to flourish. In view of these aims we strive to include the student voice which can undoubtedly contribute to an 'Epistemically Insightful' future.

Outlining Students In Research

The 'Students in research' programme organised by the LASAR Centre gives students from across the university the opportunity to develop and showcase a piece of research. The themes we offer students are designed to foster and encourage a culture of multidisciplinary exchanges rooted in academic excellence. We place high importance on providing an inclusive space, therefore, students at any stage in their academic life are welcomed; we also work with postgraduates to help support their academic development and involvement in the 'culture of research'.

Student voices inform and contribute towards the research, which in turn concerns the development of epistemic insight (EI) - Broadly conceived as knowledge about knowledge (Billingsley, 2017). EI is a process that happens in the agent's mind when the learner makes a connection about how knowledge works that makes sense to them, colloquially it can be represented as the 'aha' moment of discovery.

EI is conceptually aligned to a family of terms that we introduce to the students, our intention is to provide them a more refined understanding of EI as a practical term to help equip them both within academia and more broadly speaking. The following highlights some examples of the themes and terms we introduce to support an understanding of EI:

- **Epistemic Curiosity** - "Desire for knowledge that motivates individuals to learn new ideas, eliminate information-gaps, and solve intellectual problems" (Litman, 2012). Unlike the 'ill-fated cat' we see intellectual curiosity, or more specifically, epistemic curiosity as a way students can develop their interactions with both academic study and, more widely, the university as an institution. Ilhan reinforces this position by stating: "it is difficult even to imagine how our intellectual achievements would have been possible without the basic motivation of curiosity" (2012). In our view, being curious regarding the nature of knowledge is an essential starting point.
- **Epistemic Humility** – Understanding the power and limitations of oneself and fields of expertise. "Intellectual humility is a virtue of a person's cognitive character; this means that it disposes her to perceive and think in certain ways that help promote knowledge" (Dormandy, 2020). In such a way, epistemic humility is a balanced attitude that potentially facilitates greater appreciation for knowledge domains outside of one's own field of expertise.
- **Critical Thinking** - "Active, persistent and careful consideration of any belief or supposed form of knowledge in the light of the grounds that support it, and the further conclusions to which it tends". (Dewey, 1910). The OECD notes: "the need to build resilience to systemic risks posed by the spread of mis- and disinformation has emerged as a top priority for democratic societies" (2021). We believe that encouraging critical thinking in research is a step in the right direction.

- **Multidisciplinary Thinking** – Greater insight and appreciation for how different disciplines can help inform answers and perspectives to big questions or real-world problems through multidisciplinary approaches.
- **Epistemic Agency** – The ability, freedom and semantic awareness to approach various knowledge domains including their alternatives and “choosing among them with reason, and with the goal of acquiring knowledge” (Patton, 2019). We feel that developing this type of agency is essential for creating that ‘Aha’ moment, and in many ways, potentially kindles a deeper connection for the student, recognizing their impact in a university environment as developers of knowledge, not only learners.
- **Epistemic Tools** - A practical point of interaction - We introduce our students to the pedagogical and epistemic tools we use at LASAR as a means to help them develop an understanding of the themes described by way of something they can interact with, which is practical in nature i.e. delivering a hands on experience rather than a purely academic thought space.

The above themes and interactions are far-reaching in terms of scoping the areas in which students can develop their research and outputs. The process is focused while emphasising that students contribute to these thematic premises through their own agency. To do this, students are often supported through dialogue with an experienced researcher and mentor so that they can develop an area of research and present their project and their perspective - To provide students the optimal space to explore and develop their ideas, research support can potentially scale accordingly to the students own academic experience.

The Type of Outputs

Outputs can be decided to showcase the students’ talents and interests. We are eager to see creative outputs that demonstrate a students research and interaction, such as supporting the team at events and conferences and producing relevant material for them. Many choose to produce a publication for the EI Digest where they are writing in the style of an academic research paper or written in a more reflective and descriptive form; in both cases we encourage and help develop their outputs to include academic research and references.

Students are invited to engage with the type of analytic work that we do at LASAR, especially in terms of understanding the processes of data collection, analysis, interpretation, and dissemination, including a clear understanding of the ethical practices surrounding data and general data security. These aspects of academic life are integral to how many research centres operate, we are keen to allow students the opportunity to experience what working at a research centre is like at this level. That also means some of the outputs that students might engage with are analysis or data entry in nature.

Final Thoughts

We believe that a strong foundation built upon multidisciplinary research facilitates critical insight. On the lasting influence of education Plato suggested:

A good educational system, if maintained, engenders people of good character; and then people of good character, if they in their turn receive the benefits of an education of this kind, become better than their predecessors in every respect (Republic 424a)

Likewise, we see our continued efforts as helping to prepare and encourage students to enter the ‘future of knowledge’ as wise and compassionate epistemic agents.

References

- Billingsley, B. (2017). 'Teaching and learning about epistemic insight'. *School science review*, 98(365), pp. 59-64.
- Dewey, J. (1910). *How We Think*. Lexington: D.C. Heath and Company.
- Dormandy, K (2020). 'Intellectual Humility and Epistemic Trust'. In: M, Alfano, M, Lynch & A, Tanesini (eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of Philosophy of Humility*. Routledge.
- Ilhan, I (2012) *The Philosophy of Curiosity*. New York: Routledge
- Litman, J.A. (2012). 'Epistemic Curiosity'. In: Seel, N.M. (eds) *Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning*, pp 1162–1165
- OECD (2021) *Building the Future of Education* [Online] Available At: <https://www.oecd.org/education/future-of-education-brochure.pdf> (Accessed 26 May 2022)
- Patton, P. (2019). 'Epistemic Tools and Epistemic Agents in Scientonomy'. *Scientonomy: Journal for the Science of Science*, 3, pp. 63–89
- Plato (2008) *Republic* (Trans. Robin Waterfield). New York: Oxford University Press

Epistemic Insight

How do we solve the **Big Questions, opportunities** and **problems** of today and tomorrow?

What about if uni students from different disciplines could form a group and tackle these challenges together. Why don't we do more of that?

FIND OUT MORE AT
[futureofknowledge.com](http://futureofknowledge.com/knowledge-labs)
[/knowledge-labs](http://knowledge-labs)

